

EUbOPEN Data Management Plan

Document History

Version	Date	Description
0.1	1/10/20	Initial draft
0.2	6/10/20	Modified to better reflect EUbOPEN governance structure
0.3	7/10/20	Added Ethics part
0.4	11/10/20	Added EBI/EMBL infrastructure. Improved Scarab description. Merged comments from reviewers
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1.1	31/5/21	Month 12 review of plan, with minor modifications to reflect changes in data management workflows
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1. Introduction

EUbOPEN is an IMI-funded public-private partnership made up of 22 partners with a view to assembling open access chemogenomic libraries, chemical probes, primary patient cell-based assays and develop infrastructure and technologies to support this work.

A major output of EUbOPEN are datasets relating to the physical reagents and molecules that are generated as part of this work, which includes their characterisation and recommended use.

This Data Management Plan describes how EUbOPEN will capture, manage, curate and disseminate its data and associated metadata throughout the lifespan of the project. It is a living document and will be routinely reviewed, amended and enhanced as the project evolves. This initial version has been agreed by the project and made available within EUbOPEN as deliverable D10.8. Updated versions will be made available on an annual basis or whenever there is an agreed significant change to the data management strategy.

2. Data Flows

EUbOPEN is a highly distributed, federated, project which whilst having particular technologies and skillsets associated with particular partners, nevertheless critically depends upon the appropriate and timely flow of data and knowledge to maximise the efficiency and impacts of the project.

Figure 1: Organisation and purpose of EUbOPEN work packages and overall data flows out of the project.

Many of the work packages span across multiple partners which means that appropriate strategies for communication and effective registration and sharing of datasets is important for efficient delivery of the project's expected outputs (Open Access Deliverables).

Each academic partner site is responsible for the initial capture of the data and associated metadata generated at that site. Data from EFPIA and industrial partners will be delivered to academic partner sites with which the underlying work is associated with for incorporation in their local repositories.

Open access data and metadata will be made available in suitable formats using established repositories and through the website to the community. The scientific community is likewise encouraged to make data generated with EUbOPEN output, available.

2.1. EUbOPEN Central Database

EUbOPEN's central database (EUbScarab) aggregates key data from the academic partner sites and acts as the central clearing house for datasets before they are then assembled for approval in accordance with the project's governance and review processes. EUbScarab is a key component of the central database, ensuring that data is captured in a controlled, validated and structured manner, in accordance with FAIR principles where possible. In addition, EUbScarab data structures are being built to adopt, as far as possible, relevant ontologies and well-regard data definitions. This allows rapid and complete deposition of datasets into the public domain. EUbScarab also provides visibility to partners of the state of project progress and helps reduce duplication of effort. It is important to note that the data aggregated into EUbScarab will also remain at the data generator's site.

Not all data will be made available in EUbScarab where there are logistical or ethical reasons not to do so. For example, high-content imaging datasets or genomic data sets are extremely large and will be deposited directly into appropriate public repositories (see below) once publication of that data is approved. However, key elements or derived data will be captured in the central database either as structured data or using the EUbScarab electronic lab notebook capability. The existence and location of the full datasets will also be directly referenced in EUbScarab.

2.2. EUbOPEN Entity Identifiers

A well-defined identifier system, derived from the SGC's data management workflows refined over the last 15 years, is in place to ensure that all entities and reagents are uniquely identified and identifiable. For

example, purified proteins are labelled as the gene name followed by a letter identifying the protein isoform (as defined by NCBI Gene) and then a '-p' to identify it as a purified protein and then a three-digit number – for example BRD4A-p023. For compounds, a central compound registration workflow ensures that EUBOPEN compounds are also uniquely identified and that key metadata (e.g. source, salt form etc.) are properly captured. For example, EUB0001234bCl indicates an EUBOPEN compound number 1234, batch 2 (b) as a chloride salt.

All of these identifiers are used at the level of EUBScarab but, importantly, community accepted identifiers are also applied as appropriate. For example, HGNC gene symbols, UNIPROT IDs, CAS numbers etc. This ensures that datasets publicly deposited are able re-usable by others, whilst maintaining a reference to associated experiments within EUBOPEN.

Recognisable and unique EUBOPEN identifiers are applied to chemical probes and chemogenomic libraries once approved and deposited. These identifiers are used as keys within all depositions.

2.3. EUBOPEN Data Sharing

EUBOPEN has implemented an EUBOPEN database (EUBScarab) for internal data sharing purposes of activities and data related to outputs of EUBOPEN. EUBOPEN outputs related to and declared Open Access Deliverables such as reagent information (e.g. novel vectors, constructs) and derived information (e.g. macromolecular structures) will be deposited into well-regarded sustainable public repositories such as the wwPDB and relevant EBI databases. Where there are no such repositories in existence, datasets will be deposited within Zenodo, providing DOIs for unique and findable identification. Once chemogenomic libraries, chemical probes and patient cell-based assay datasets as defined in Appendix 13 of the consortium agreement are approved and declared Open Access Deliverables, these packages of data as well as associated metadata and characterisation data will be made deposited into ChEMBL and associated public repositories and then made available via the EUBOPEN Gateway (<https://gateway.eubopen.org>). This web site is being custom-built upon the ChEMBL platform and provides a fast-track route to deposition of EUBOPEN data into ChEMBL and Open Targets. The Gateway documents the availability of the relevant EUBOPEN data, sign-posting to their sustainable locations or providing data mining and visualisation tools to allow researchers interactive and intuitive access. This will enable researchers to understand the breadth and depth of EUBOPEN's output as well as perform basic hypothesis generation operations and the ability to download subsets of interest for further analysis and incorporation in ML/AI methods, for example.

Figure 2: Key data flows involving the major academic EUBOPEN partners with dissemination approaches.

2.4. EUbOPEN Data Publication

In addition to deposition of chemical probe, chemogenomic library and patient cell-based assay datasets following package approval, other data may be released subject to the following processes.

For release of chemical probes, chemogenomics libraries and human tissue assays, the procedure in the management structure outline of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement will be followed. For other dataset release, a release request containing as minimum an abstract, appropriate identifiers, adherence to data standards, quality control compliance and proposed location for sustainable deposition must be provided. These requests will be collated by WP11 and discussed by the PCT within four weeks of receipt and may request further information or work to be performed to refine the dataset's quality. The request, or the refined request, should be presented for approval to the EMC at their regular meetings or at extraordinary meetings, if necessary.

All peer-reviewed scientific publications will be open access (free-of-charge online access for any user). For example, manuscripts for which a member of the academic EUbOPEN partners is the corresponding author will be promptly submitted to a pre-preprint server such as bioRxiv or ChemRxiv, provided they have been approved for public release by the contributing organisations. Details of any publication and an electronic copy of the published version will be provided to the IMI2 JU within two (2) months following publication. These depositions will also be listed within the EUbOPEN website and EUbOPEN Gateway. Details regarding the procedure to be followed for the submission of the student thesis are set out in the consortium agreement.

We encourage EUbOPEN members to apply their ORCID(s) (Open Research and Contributor Identifiers) to all publications and data depositions where possible.

3. Data Types and Definitions

There are a wide range of data types that are generated and shared within and beyond EUbOPEN. Below, we document the major data types along with expected metadata and standards.

Data description	Chemogenomics library package
Data type	List of component small molecules that form the library along with characterisation data (see other data types for information about individual components)
WP(s)	1, 2
Primary format	PDF, web pages, tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	UOXF, UTOR, GUF, KI, EFPIA and Associated Partners, Academic collaborators
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN Chemogenomic library ID, EUbOPEN compound IDs, NCBI Gene IDs, UniProt IDs. ChEMBL IDs. Document DOI
Metadata	Package version. Compound molecular weight, molecular formula, IUPAC name, logP, tPSA, storage conditions, selectivity, cell-based data, co-crystal structures, synthetic routes
Community standards / ontology	As part of EUbOPEN's scientific governance process, a proposal for a standard chemogenomics library ontology and standards will be presented and approved in advance of any release
Quality control (where appropriate)	Peer review by internal and external scientific committee
Expected Data Volume	100 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, UTOR, GUF
Data owner	UOXF, UTOR, GUF

What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. Components of the library will also be deposited in ChEMBL, Open Targets, BioImage archive etc. as appropriate

Data description	Small molecule (Compound) <i>in-silico</i> information
Data type(s)	EuBOPEN Compound ID, tabular metadata, 2D structure information
WP(s)	1-9
Primary format	Tabular data, SD-file
Acquisition source	Vendor or in-project chemistry
Identifier(s)	SMILES, InChI, IUPAC identifier
Metadata	Batch identifier, Source, Source ID, cross-referenced IDs in other repositories (e.g. ChEBI, PubChem, ChEMBL), molecular weight, (c)LogP, salt information
Community standards/ontology	MIABE, ChEMBL (www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl), InChI
Quality control (where appropriate)	Calibration of HPLC system
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	EuBOPEN central database
Data owner	EuBOPEN
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	n/a
Data sharing & sustainability plan	Compound information associated with approved chemogenomic libraries and chemical probes will be pushed into the EuBOPEN Gateway and ChEMBL

Data description	Compound purity
Data type	a) Compound purity in % according to HPLC b) Identity according to MS c) absorbance spectrum (full wavelength scan)
WP(s)	1 and 2
Primary format	Tabular (CSV) and image (for spectra)
Acquisition source	HPLC-MS
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN Compound ID
Metadata	HPLC system, parameters relating to data acquisition
Community standards/ontology	n/a
Quality control (where appropriate)	Calibration of HPLC system
Expected Data Volume	1 TB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF and EuBOPEN Scarab
Data owner	GUF, LUMC
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	n/a

Data sharing & sustainability plan	Compound purity information associated with approved chemogenomic libraries and chemical probes will be pushed into the EuBOPEN Gateway and ChEMBL
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Data description	Compound effect on general autophagy flux
Data type	Autophagy flux over time and growth rate
WP(s)	2, 3
Primary format	Table (CSV)
Acquisition source	IncuCyte
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN Compound ID, ATCC cell line ID (https://www.lgcstandards-atcc.org/Products/Cells_and_Microorganisms/Cell_Lines/Human.aspx)
Metadata	Assay parameters. Cell confluence, total integrated fluorescence green and red channels
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Effect of control compounds (DMSO, Torin1, Bafilomycin A1)
Expected Data Volume	Approximately 50TB, primarily for raw image data
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. BioImage Archive (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/). ChEMBL

Data description	Cellular viability assay (Alamar Blue, XTT or similar)
Data type	Numeric value (IC ₅₀ (M) or % living cells)
WP(s)	2, 3, 5
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	n/a
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID, ATCC cell line ID
Metadata	Assay conditions, compound concentration, incubation times, cellular sample preparation
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	IC ₅₀ or % living cells for reference compounds
Expected Data Volume	10GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF, UTOR, LUMC
Data owner	GUF, UTOR, LUMC
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	Cytotoxicity data of compounds
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Data type	Numeric - % living cells, growth rate (GR), percentage of gated cell population, normalized cell count/nuclei count. Cell images
WP(s)	2
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	CQ1 confocal quantitative image cytometer
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN Compound ID, EuBOPEN cytotox experimental ID (CQ1-ctfxxx), ATCC cell line ID
Metadata	Assay parameters including compound concentration, incubation times, cellular sample preparation
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compounds
Expected Data Volume	Raw data (pictures) approx. 100 TB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. BioImage Archive (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/). ChEMBL

Data description	Mitophagy flux
Data type	Compound effect upon mitophagy flux over time and growth rate
WP(s)	2, 3
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	IncuCyte
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN Compound ID, ATCC cell line ID
Metadata	Compound concentration, incubation times, confluence, total integrated fluorescence green/red, cellular sample preparation
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Effect of control compounds (DMSO, TorinI, BafilomycinA 1, Antimycin/Oligomycin, CCCP)
Expected Data Volume	50 TB (raw images)
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. BioImage Archive (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/). ChEMBL

Data description	In vitro protein kinase activity data
Data type	Thermo Fisher Omnia Kinase assay outputs
WP(s)	2, 5
Primary format	Tabular (CSV) format for IC ₅₀ values
Acquisition source	Fluorescence reader
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID, EuBOPEN protein ID

Metadata	Substrate identity, substrate concentration used, co-substrate concentration used (if applicable), co-substrate identity (if applicable), compound concentration
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference Compound IC ₅₀
Expected Data Volume	10GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF and EUbOPEN SCarab
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	In vitro GPCR functional activity data
Data type	PRESTO-Tango GPCR beta-arrestin recruitment
WP(s)	1, 3
Primary format	Tabular (CSV) format for %max activity, %inhibition and EC ₅₀ values
Acquisition source	Fluorescence reader
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN compound ID, EUbOPEN protein ID
Metadata	Cell line, compound concentration, reference agonist
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference Compound EC ₅₀
Expected Data Volume	10GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	KI and EUbOPEN SCarab
Data owner	KI
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	In vitro GPCR binding data
Data type	GPCR radioligand displacement
WP(s)	1, 3
Primary format	Tabular (CSV) format for %inhibition and Ki (M) values
Acquisition source	Scintillation counter
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN compound ID, EUbOPEN protein ID
Metadata	Cell line, tissue, radioligand, reference ligand, compound concentration
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference Compound Ki
Expected Data Volume	10GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	KI and EUbOPEN SCarab
Data owner	KI (UNC)
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	Cellular migration assay
Data type	Incucyte scratch assay, EC ₅₀ or % wound closure
WP(s)	3, 5
Primary format	Numeric value (IC ₅₀ , (M) or %)
Acquisition source	Microscopy
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID, ATCC cell line ID
Metadata	Time observed, compound concentration
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compound EC ₅₀ or % wound closure
Expected Data Volume	10GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	Nuclear Receptor compound activity
Data type	Single point (active/inactive), fold activation, EC ₅₀ or IC ₅₀ value (in μ M), efficacy (max. fold activation)
WP(s)	1, 2
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	Microscopy
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID, ATCC cell line ID
Metadata	Compound concentration. Assay parameters including incubation times, cellular sample preparation
Community standards/ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, Cellosaurus
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compounds
Expected Data Volume	10 TB (images)
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL. BioImage Archive (https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/)

Data description	Measurement of enzymatic activity or protein-protein interactions in cell-free assays
Data type	Quantitative TR-FRET, Fluorescence Intensity and Polarization, AlphaScreen and Alpha Lisa
WP(s)	5
Primary format	CSV Data, GraphPad files
Acquisition source	Plate readers
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID, EuBOPEN Protein ID

Metadata	Protein ID, Substrate ID, Assays conditions i.e buffer composition, positive controls, assay time
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE
Quality control (where appropriate)	Performance of assay confirmed by appropriate controls and references, Appropriate Z' and signal-to-base and signal-to-noise
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, GUF, KI, LUMC, UNIVDUN, UTOR
Data owner	UOXF, GUF, KI, LUMC, UNIVDUN, UTOR
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets, ChEMBL

Data description	Mass spectrometry-based protein information
Data type	Peptide derived precursor ion and fragment ion spectra, protein abundance profiles
WP(s)	3,5,8
Primary format	Instrument raw format, mzXML, mzData, text
Acquisition source	Mass spectrometry
Identifier(s)	UniProt protein ID
Metadata	Protein source, treatment, sample preparation technique, MS instrument information, acquisition methods
Community standards / ontology	Minimum information about a proteomics experiment (MIAPE)
Quality control (where appropriate)	Standard samples
Expected Data Volume	1-2TB (expected)
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	ETH Zürich
Data owner	ETH Zürich
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets, PeptideAtlas, PRIDE

Data description	Cellular target engagement data (NanoBRET)
Data type	IC50 or % tracer displacement
WP(s)	2, 3, 5
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	Fluorescence plate reader
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN compound ID, EUbOPEN protein ID
Metadata	Identifier, tracer identity, target identity (construct ID), tracer concentration used
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compound tracer displacement
Expected Data Volume	10 GB

Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, GUF, UTOR
Data owner	UOXF, GUF, UTOR
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets, ChEMBL

Data description	Dissociation constant and thermodynamic parameters of protein-ligand binding determined by ITC
Data type	K_d , ΔH , ΔS , ΔG , stoichiometry
WP(s)	2, 5
Primary format	Tabular (CSV) and analysis file (raw data plot as image/graph)
Acquisition source	ITC instrument
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN Compound ID, EUbOPEN protein ID
Metadata	Acquisition parameters.
Community standards/ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compounds
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, GUF, KI
Data owner	UOXF, GUF, KI
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets, ChEMBL

Data description	Melting temperature shift (ΔT_m) analyses for protein-ligand binding
Data type	ΔT_m and potentially fold changes of ΔT_m (numbers with digits)
WP(s)	2, 5
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	RT-PCR instruments
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN compound ID, EUbOPEN protein ID
Metadata	Acquisition parameters
Community standards/ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compounds
Expected Data Volume	5 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, GUF, KI, UTOR
Data owner	UOXF, GUF, KI, UTOR
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	Sequences of proteins generated for structural and chemical biology purposes
Data type	Protein sequence

WP(s)	4
Primary format	FASTA format
Acquisition source	n/a
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN protein ID, UniProt ID, NCBI Gene ID
Metadata	Molecular weight, pI
Community standards / ontology	Protein nomenclature: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/doc/internatprot_nomenguide/ FASTA sequence format: http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/blastcgihelp.shtml
Quality control (where appropriate)	Intact mass verification (Mass-spec)
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, GUF, KI, UNIVDUN, UTOR, LUMC
Data owner	UOXF, GUF, KI, UNIVDUN, UTOR, LUMC
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. BioStudies.

Data description	Macromolecular structure of proteins, often with ligands (e.g. small molecules, antibody) bound
Data type	Coordinates derived from protein crystallography and cryo-EM studies
WP(s)	6, 8
Primary format	PDB, mmCIF file formats and EMD for cryo-EM
Acquisition source	Diamond Light Source, eBIC, ESRF, ALS, SLS, APS
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN protein ID, EUbOPEN Compound ID (as required), PDB ID, EMD ID
Metadata	Crystallographic and Cryo-EM sample information. Acquisition parameters. Data processing and model building software and parameters. wwPDB validation report.
Community standards/ontology	wwPDB: http://mmcif.wwpdb.org/ https://www.emdataresource.org/conventions.html
Quality control (where appropriate)	EUbOPEN structure quality criteria. Community structural biology standards.
Expected Data Volume	10 TB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	Acquisition sources and UOXF, UNIVDUN, GUF, UTOR where data processing and model building are performed
Data owner	UOXF, UNIVDUN, GUF, UTOR
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	wwPDB database. EUbOPEN Gateway. https://www.emdataresource.org/

Data description	Chemical Probes Package
Data type	Chemical probe definition, properties, characterisation and annotations (see other data types for more details about individual components)
WP(s)	7

Primary format	PDF, CSV for tabular data
Acquisition source	UOXF, UTOR, GUF, EFPIA Partners, Academic collaborators
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN Chemical Probe ID
Metadata	Package version. Molecular weight, molecular formula, IUPAC name, logP, TPSA, storage conditions, selectivity, cell-based data, co-crystal structures, synthetic routes
Community standards / ontology	EuBOPEN chemical probe packages adhere to the standards defined by the chemical probes portal project and SGC-lead community expectations
Quality control (where appropriate)	Peer review by internal and external scientific committee
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	UOXF, UTOR, GUF, LUMC, UNIVDUN
Data owner	UOXF, UTOR, GUF, LUMC, UNIVDUN
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. Components of the package will also be deposited in ChEMBL, BioImage archive etc. as appropriate

Data description	Identification and visualisation of biological and chemical components by Raman spectroscopy
Data type	Raman spectra and images thereof
WP(s)	8
Primary format	WIP data files
Acquisition source	Spectrometer
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID
Metadata	Acquisition parameters
Community standards / ontology	MIABE
Quality control (where appropriate)	Reference compounds
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	None
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway

Data description	CRC cell assay protocols and results of compound screening
Data type	Text, numbers
WP(s)	9
Primary format	Tabular (CSV), cell images
Acquisition source	Microscopy
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN compound ID. ATCC cell line ID (where appropriate)

Metadata	Patient clinical/health data (e.g. age, diagnosis, disease activity, medications, etc), clinical sample (e.g. cell count/viability), reagents (e.g. batch of compound plate)
Community standards / ontology	PubChem, ChEMBL, http://www.openmicroscopy.org/ , EFO
Quality control (where appropriate)	Biological replicates
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	GUF
Data owner	GUF
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	Personal data: health and genetic data (DNA sequencing and RNA-seq). Data are pseudonymised.
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EuBOPEN Gateway (signposting), ChEMBL. Identifiable data associated with sequencing efforts will be deposited within the EGA (https://ega-archive.org)

Data description	Screening of chemical probes' and chemogenomic compounds' effect on liver in NASH model
Data type	AlphaLISA analysis (pro collagen 1)
WP(s)	9
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	Perkin Elmer AlphaLISA reader
Identifier(s)	EuBOPEN Compound ID
Metadata	Assay and acquisition parameters. Patient data are deidentified.
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE
Quality control (where appropriate)	Biological replicates
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	KI
Data owner	KI
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	The study is approved by the local ethical review board. Patient data are deidentified.
Data sharing & sustainability plan	Non-identifiable data will be provided via the EuBOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

Data description	Cell assay protocols and results of compound screening
Data type	Text, numbers
WP(s)	9
Primary format	Csv, doc
Acquisition source	n/a
Identifier(s)	disease, patient, sample, assay, compound
Metadata	Patient clinical/health data (e.g. age, diagnosis, disease activity, medications, etc), clinical sample (e.g. cell count/viability), reagents (e.g. batch of compound plate), assay readout (e.g. result type, uom)
Community standards / ontology	PubChem, ChEMBL
Quality control (where appropriate)	n/a

Expected Data Volume	<1GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	KI
Data owner	KI
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	Personal data: health and genetic data (DNA SNP and RNA-seq). Data are pseudonymised.
Data sharing & sustainability plan	EUbOPEN Data Portal as summary data, EGA data repository for identifiable data

Data description	Screening of chemical probes' and compounds' effects on B cell function (MS patients)
Data type	B-cell assay
WP(s)	9
Primary format	Tabular (CSV)
Acquisition source	Biorad Bio-Plex, ELISpot MabTech IRIS
Identifier(s)	EUbOPEN Compound ID. Pseudonymised patient ID code combined with compound ID code
Metadata	Assay and acquisition parameters. Patient description, including diagnosis, treatment etc
Community standards / ontology	BioAssay Ontology, MIABE, EFO
Quality control (where appropriate)	Biological replicates
Expected Data Volume	10 GB
Expected primary storage location before public deposition	KI
Data owner	KI
What regulatory or ethical considerations, if any?	GDPR – the metadata contains sensitive personal information; the study is approved by the local ethical review board
Data sharing & sustainability plan	Non-identifiable data will be provided via the EUbOPEN Gateway as part of other data sets. ChEMBL

4. Data Security

EUbOPEN expects its data related to Open Access Deliverables to be made available in an open access manner. However, before this occurs, it is important that the security of the data is assured.

Data security is primarily the responsibility of the generating site. Each partner has well-defined organisation information governance and data management policies and local expertise to support this. In particular, potentially disclosive information (e.g. patient demographic or clinical/phenotypic data) is only stored at originating EUbOPEN sites and is tightly governed by local ethics approvals. These ethics approvals, which are listed in the table below, can be provided to the IMI JU upon request.

WP	Cell/tissue type	Beneficiary access to biobank	Ethical approval no
9	Colon biopsies, blood samples	KI	2019-04553
9	Colon biopsies	KI	2017-1865-31/2
9	Blood samples from healthy volunteers	KI	2015/2001-31/2

9	Colorectal Cancer	GSH	274-18_iBDF 4/09_SGI-12-2018
9	Blood and cerebrospinal fluid from healthy volunteers	KI	2018/534-32
9	Blood and cerebrospinal fluid from patients with MS	KI	2009/2107-31/2, 2015/1280-32, 2017/1347-32, 2018/534-32, 2020-06295
9	Liver cells from patients undergoing surgery or transplantation	KI	2017/269-31
9	iPSCs	McGill	2019-5374/F9- 55426, A03-M19- 22A/22.03.027

The EUbOPEN central database is housed on UOXF infrastructure and maintained directly by members of the EUbOPEN consortium. Backups of all data are made nightly to tape, which is then stored offsite, and also to off-site disk storage. Access to the underlying infrastructure (services, storage, backup) is only possible to key UOXF members. Brian Marsden (UOXF) is responsible for the EUbOPEN central database infrastructure.

The central database components are protected by login/password combination that is managed by UOXF. Scarab routinely logs all operations including logins, reports run and changes to data.

The EUbOPEN Data Gateway is housed within the EMBL/EBI infrastructure and maintained by EMBL-EBI members of the EUbOPEN consortium. Andrew Leach (EMBL) is responsible for the EUbOPEN Data Gateway. EMBL-EBI operates its public services across two data centres. In each data centre services are hosted in virtual machines or containers operating over VMware. VMware is an Enterprise scale commercial product with many high-availability features allowing for workloads to migrate across a pool of machines as software patches are applied. It is common practice to operate multiple instances of a service in each data centre which are then load balanced between the data centres to deliver the visible public service. This allows for the interruption of a single service instance for maintenance with the remaining instances taking up the extra load, or for a single data centre to go off-line while the service continues to be available to the public. EMBL-EBI has a strict internal Electronic Data Security Policy (EDSP), the implementation of which is overseen by the EMBL-EBI IT Security Steering Committee (EISSC) consisting of senior staff members and representatives of the Technical Services Cluster. The Committee advises the Directors of EMBL-EBI, who ultimately approve the EDSP. EDSP defines different security levels for different types of human data depending on the risks presented by accidental unauthorised use of such data. Appropriate measures are taken so that this will not happen. Additionally, EMBL has established the Human Data Committee (HDC), advising the Director General and the Directors of EMBL-EBI on issues related to public release or necessary security levels of various types of human data. The EDSP is periodically reviewed and adjusted according to the recommendations of EDSP and HDC.

Key EUbOPEN documents, such as reports, minutes, SOPs etc. are shared within an instance of the cloud-based Microsoft Teams platform and managed by GUF.

No joint controllership of personal data within EUbOPEN in the sense of art. 26 of the GDPR will occur. The purpose for collecting and processing of Personal data will be determined by the appointed respective data controller pertaining to that specific personal data. In accordance with GDPR personal data will only be processed by data processors assigned by the data controller in accordance with art. 28 of the GDPR.

KI, GSH and McGill confirm that all research planned in EUbOPEN comply with respective national legal frameworks for the rights of data subjects and the processing of genetic and health data.

For Sweden: no special derogations are relevant to the planned activities in EUbOPEN pertaining to the rights of data subjects or the processing of genetic and/or health data. KI confirms compliance with all applicable Swedish legal frameworks.

For Germany: no special derogations apply in Germany affecting planned activities within this project.

For Canada: no special derogations apply in Canada affecting planned activities within this project, and McGill confirms compliance with all applicable Canadian legal frameworks.

For the Netherlands: we confirm that all research activities planned in EUbOPEN for LUMC comply with national legalisation and permissions. We will also adhere to the LUMC guidelines for data management that are for LUMC-use only. These are available upon request.

Any transfer of personal data within EUbOPEN from the EU to a non-EU country will be done in accordance with Chapter V of the GDPR.

The concerned consortium members have lawful basis (in the sense of art. 6 of GDPR) for further processing of previously collected personal data and confirm that the appropriate technical and organisational measures to safeguard the rights of the data subjects are in place.

KI – Further processing of collected data will take place for patient-derived tissues from MS, liver fibrosis as well as IBD patients. KI confirms it has lawful basis to process the data. The technical and organisational measures to safeguard the rights of data subjects follow national laws and include restricted access buildings, technical authorization systems and automatic logs to monitor access.

GSH – Legal basis for the use of patient data is the consent to iBDF. A general concept for data protection has been implemented, which has been positively evaluated by the local data protection officer. The guidelines regulate the data use, storage and access to the database (CentraXX) and appropriate technical and organisational measures are in place.

McGill – All safeguards are in place to ensure donor identity is protected. Blockchain encryption is used to protect patient clinical files and history related to each iPSC stored in the MNI's electronic database (LORIS). All necessary permissions are in place to apply for additional access to patient data through the MNI's biorepository tissue data committee if increased access is required.

Patient data will be stored in a non-anonymised way at respective sites for the following reasons. Access to patient-related data such as diagnosis, disease state, past and current treatments etc. are essential to increase the translational value of the research data obtained within EUbOPEN. Access to and use of such data will be in tight collaboration with responsible clinicians and biobanks, adhering to all laws and regulations on national, international and institutional levels.

Personal data, including medical data, will be collected in conjunction with the biological samples in accordance with respective ethical approval, to correlate experimental in vitro findings to disease states and treatments. This represents an important aspect of EUbOPEN research and will increase the translational value of our findings. To protect all participating subjects, collection of personal data will strictly adhere to

applicable international, national and EU laws and regulations such as the GDPR. All patient identification data processed in EUBOPEN will be pseudonymised according to the procedures of each established biobank. These procedures have been approved by the local ethical committees and collection of personal data is in accordance with respective applicable national and/or EU laws. Processing of personal data only takes place after written free informed consent has been given by the data subjects. All data used in publications in any format, will be grouped or aggregated and quality assured prior to release to the scientific community and to the public.

Traffic to and from all EUBOPEN web-based informatics resources, including the central database components and the Gateway, is protected by the use of https (secure sockets layer) encryption. Access to web-based internal resources is controlled by an IP-address access control list both at the UOXF firewall and also individual servers. There is no direct access to the underlying database platforms from outside of the local infrastructure at UOXF.

Data transfer from EUBOPEN sites to the central database is planned to be performed in two ways. Firstly, where either data volume is low or the site does not have its own local Scarab implementation, direct entry into EUBScarab will be possible. Secondly, where local Scarab implementations exist, it is planned to implement bridging pipelines that will harvest data from these Scarab databases and push directly into EUBScarab. This will be tightly controlled via IP address access lists and user authentication processes. All transfers will be documented in EUBScarab to include metadata pertaining to the operation performed and the data transferred, for the purposes of auditing.

5. FAIR Compliance

EUBOPEN is committed to ensuring that all outputs are compliant with FAIR principles. The effective use of community agreed data standards and ontologies along with well-defined data dissemination pathways forms the basis for EUBOPEN's drive to develop sustainable infrastructures that have FAIR principles embedded as a fundamental requirement.

To support this effort, EUBOPEN is working directly with the FAIRplus IMI consortium who are providing advice and support as a focussed collaboration with WP10.

With reference to the approaches and definitions detailed above, we summarise our overall approach to ensuring FAIR compliance below.

5.1. Findable Data

A pre-requisite for findable data is that it is uniquely identifiable. The EUBOPEN identifier systems provide a clear approach to fulfil this requirement. These identifiers, in conjunction with community-standard identifiers, ensure that users of EUBOPEN data may locate data of interest. Where there are key documents or software generated, version control is actively used.

The EUBOPEN Gateway will be registered at fairsharing.org and will provide static URLs containing EUBOPEN identifiers as a further means to find datasets quickly. Generic metadata supporting datasets (e.g. date stamp, authors, title etc.) will be exposed in the Gateway for indexing by other resources including major web-search engines. Direct functionality will be provided in the Gateway providing the capability to use keywords or identifiers to search against the datasets and their metadata to support rapid finding of relevant datasets.

5.2. Accessible Data

EUBOPEN's mandate is to provide open access to its Open Access Deliverables in a sustainable manner. Data generated and released by EUBOPEN will be sign-posted from the web-based EUBOPEN Gateway. In addition to providing direct and sustainable links to depositions at the EUBOPEN Gateway itself, it will also

linked to depositions made elsewhere, via persistent DOIs where possible. Any software required to read or operate upon the files will be versioned, made available via EUBOPEN's GitHub public account where possible, and associated with the data itself.

Whilst it will be possible to download datasets (see Interoperable Data, below), the Gateway will provide web-based functionality to mine, subset, visualise and further download data of interest as well as supporting basic hypothesis generation capabilities.

5.3. Interoperable Data

EUBOPEN is committed to making its released data as compatible with existing *in silico* workflows, pipelines and software applications. In particular, the ability for EFPIA partners and other interested third parties to be able to access and integrate EUBOPEN data without significant data extraction, transformation and loading operations is of particular importance. Our expectation that EUBOPEN datasets will provide a rich field for ML/AI methods development also depends upon this.

As part of our open access principles, all datasets and their metadata will be deposited and provided via the Gateway in community standard formats which are non-proprietary unless this is entirely unavoidable. Community-standard identifiers for entities, where appropriate, will be included as part of the metadata to allow facile reference to other third-party datasets.

Where there are no accepted ontologies or data standards available for a given data type, EUBOPEN will work with the relevant communities where possible to assist in their definition.

5.4. Data Re-use

EUBOPEN believes that rapidly providing reproducible data to the community is a critical aspect of its outputs. As part of the data flow process, EUBOPEN is able to capture all aspects of data generation for the purposes of reproducibility by others. All datasets on Open Access Deliverables will be provided as open access with no restriction upon use, using a license provided by Creative Commons. Software generated by EUBOPEN are made available via the project's public GitHub account.

All data generated by EUBOPEN will be deposited into sustainable public repositories including the EUBOPEN Gateway. This will ensure that it is re-usable and findable following the completion of the EUBOPEN project.

6. Ethical and Legal Considerations

EUBOPEN captures a minimal set of information on participants for the purposes of communication and sharing of knowledge and datasets. These include e.g. names, contact information, affiliations, email addresses and dietary restrictions (for the purpose of organizing meetings and conferences). Furthermore, personal data including meta-data obtained within WP9 is processed within EUBOPEN. All processing is performed in compliance with applicable data protection legislation such as the GDPR – see details below. All personal data will be treated as defined in the Consortium Agreement, section 4.5:

“During the Project, each Beneficiary may as part of its activities under an Action individually or jointly with other Beneficiaries or Third Parties Process Personal Data. In such event, the Beneficiary shall be individually (or collectively with other Beneficiaries and/or Third Parties, as the case may be) responsible for ensuring that the Personal Data are Processed in accordance with the applicable legislation and Appendix 2. The Beneficiaries must Process Personal Data under the Agreement in compliance with applicable EU and national laws on data protection (including, the General Data Protection Regulation). Each Beneficiary

represents and warrants (i) that any Personal Data required for use in the Project or generated during the Project, that are Processed by it will be Processed in accordance with all relevant laws and regulations regarding the Processing, of Personal Data and (ii) that any applicable authorisations from relevant supervisory authorities and informed consents of the Data Subjects – in so far needed under applicable law - required for performing the Action will be obtained prior to the commencement of the respective part of the Allocated Work. The Beneficiaries may grant their personnel access only to such Personal Data if this is strictly necessary for implementing, performing, managing and monitoring the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement. When Processing Personal Data under the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement, the relevant Beneficiaries will comply with the terms and conditions as set out in Appendix 2. y shall be individually (or collectively with other Beneficiaries and/or Third Parties, as the case may be) responsible for ensuring that the Personal Data are Processed in accordance with the applicable legislation and Appendix 2. The Beneficiaries must Process Personal Data under the Agreement in compliance with applicable EU and national laws on data protection (including, the General Data Protection Regulation). Each Beneficiary represents and warrants (i) that any Personal Data required for use in the Project or generated during the Project, that are Processed by it will be Processed in accordance with all relevant laws and regulations regarding the Processing, of Personal Data and (ii) that any applicable authorisations from relevant supervisory authorities and informed consents of the Data Subjects – in so far needed under applicable law - required for performing the Action will be obtained prior to the commencement of the respective part of the Allocated Work. The Beneficiaries may grant their personnel access only to such Personal Data if this is strictly necessary for implementing, performing, managing and monitoring the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement. When Processing Personal Data under the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement, the relevant Beneficiaries will comply with the terms and conditions as set out in Appendix 2.”

Appendix 2 to the Consortium Agreement: Actions involving Personal Data

1. APPLICATION

The Action consists of different Work Packages. Each Work Package may in turn consist of different tasks under which a Beneficiary may potentially Process Personal Data as either a Controller, Joint Controller or Processor and potentially engage a Third Party in such Processing, which may also be acting as a Controller or Processor.

Beneficiaries will have to comply (and procure that the Third Parties assigned by them will comply) with the following principles and applicable laws and regulations when collecting, processing, storing, using or transferring any Personal Data for activities conducted, sponsored, supported or funded pursuant to the Action.

To the extent that, according to the Data Protection Legislation, the information on the Processing of the Personal Data shall be provided to and/or any consent (if and where required) shall be granted by the legal guardian of the Data Subject, the provisions in that regard of this Appendix 2 regarding the Data Subject shall apply, where and to the extent relevant, to the Data Subject’s legal guardian instead.

2. ADDITIONAL DEFINITIONS

“Controller” shall mean in respect of any particular transfer of Personal Data the Beneficiary which, alone or jointly with another Beneficiary or a Third Party, determines the purposes and means of Processing.

“Data Subject” shall mean an identified or identifiable natural person, including Donors. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

“Joint Controllers” shall mean where two or more Controllers jointly determine the purpose and means of the Processing of the Personal Data.

“Process” or “Processing” or “Processed” shall mean any operation or set of operations which is performed on Personal Data or sets of Personal Data whether or not by automated means, such as the obtaining, collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure, by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

“Processor” shall mean any Beneficiary or Third Party that Processes Personal Data on behalf and according to the instructions of a Controller.

3. ACTIONS REGARDING PERSONAL DATA

3.1 **General obligations of the Beneficiaries when Processing Personal Data (when Beneficiaries are acting as a Controller).** When Personal Data are introduced to the Action by or on behalf of a Beneficiary, such Beneficiary must ensure that:

- (1) the Personal Data are Processed in accordance with all laws, rules, regulations and guidelines applicable to their collection, use, handling, disposal and further Processing of Personal Data, including – without limitation – data protection legislations (to the extent applicable on a Beneficiary Processing Personal Data), such as the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (EU), “GDPR” (or succeeding regulations) and implementing national data protection laws as applicable and the Standards for Individually Identifiable Health Information (45 CFR Parts 160 and 164, the "Privacy Rule") promulgated pursuant to the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 (USA), and the Personal Health Information Protection Act of 2004 (Canada), all as updated from time to time as applicable (**“Data Protection Legislation”**)
- (2) if applicable, and in so far and to the extent required under the Data Protection Legislation, the Personal Data are collected with voluntarily given informed consent covering the activities of the Action, including the collection, processing, storage, use and transfer including the addressees of the transfer of the Personal Data as provided for under the Action, such informed consent may

be revocable any time with effect for the future (taking into account that the consequences of such withdrawal may be restricted under the Data Protection Legislation),¹

- (3) to the extent required under Data Protection Legislation, the responsible ethics committee/Institutional Review Board (IRB) has given its approval to the collection, processing, storage, use and transfer of the Personal Data under the Action, and
- (4) if applicable, , the Data Subjects have not withdrawn their informed consents (taking into account that the consequences of such withdrawal may be restricted under the Data Protection Legislation).
- (5) The Beneficiary shall procure that the Personal Data are (i) Processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, (ii) collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes, (iii) adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are Processed (or further compatible processing if permitted under the Data Protection Legislation) (iv) accurate and (where necessary) kept up to date (v) not kept for a period longer than necessary (except if permitted by the Data Protection Legislation if appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented) and (vi) Processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the Personal Data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures.

3.2 Beneficiaries shall ensure that the Processing of Personal Data is subject to appropriate security measures that: (a) are able to ensure the ongoing confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services (b) where appropriate result in pseudonymisation and/or encryption of Personal Data; (c) are able to restore the availability and access to the Personal Data in a timely manner in the event of a physical or technical incident; and (d) include a process for regularly testing, assessing and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures for ensuring the security of the Processing.

3.3 Beneficiaries shall ensure that personnel dealing with the Processing of Personal Data are obliged to data secrecy under an enforceable confidentiality duty and that they are informed about the obligations under the Data Protection Legislation and contractual provisions regarding data protection and that they will act in accordance with those obligations and provisions.

3.4 To the extent a Sub-Contractor Processes Personal Data, the appointing Beneficiary will select such Sub-Contractor considering the adequacy of the technical and organizational measures for the protection of Personal data implemented by the Sub-Contractor and will oblige such Sub-Contractor in accordance with this Consortium Agreement. If the Sub-Contractor and/or its Processing is located in countries outside the European Economic Area which do not offer an adequate level of protection, the appointing Beneficiary will procure that the Sub-Contractor has or will implement an adequate level

¹ The Beneficiaries should consider to agree on a data protection concept including the minimum requirements for informed consents, if required under Data Protection Legislation, such as that (i) the purpose of use in informed consent must cover activities under the Action (and further processing in so far allowed under Data Protection Legislation), (ii) informed consent must allow for transfer of data and samples to academic and commercial entities inside and outside EU, and (iii) the informed consent must be voluntary with a right to withdraw at any time(taking into account that the consequences of such withdrawal may be restricted under the Data Protection Legislation).

of protection, according to Chapter V of the GDPR (to the extent applicable) e.g. where applicable by executing model clauses in the form issued by the European Commission. or competent data protection authority (the case being).

- 3.5 Beneficiaries will not introduce to the Action or Process Personal Data for reasons unrelated to the Action, unless (i) all legal requirements under applicable Data Protection Legislation for the collection, processing, storage, use and transfer of the Personal Data under the Action or under subsequent compatible processing (such as that the informed consent – to the extent it is relied upon – allows for such use or subsequent processing is allowed under the Data Protection Legislation) are fulfilled, and (ii) prior written approval of the competent ethics committee/IRB is obtained, to the extent required under applicable Data Protection Legislation. When a Beneficiary obtains Personal Data from a source where the collection was made for reasons unrelated to the Action the Beneficiaries shall need to become informed about the origin of the Personal Data.
- 3.6 Each Beneficiary is solely responsible for evaluating its role as Controller, Joint Controller or Processor in relation to a Work Package and/or a Work Package task under the Project such Beneficiary participates in.
- 3.7 **Controller to Controller Actions.** To the extent a Beneficiary introduces to the Action Personal Data and thereby enables other Beneficiaries or Third Parties to access and Process such Personal Data within the Project independent from specific instructions regarding the handling of Personal Data (“**Controller to Controller**”), the introducing Beneficiary and the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party are additionally obliged as follows:
- (1) Personal Data shall be accessed only for the purpose of the Project and the corresponding agreements, i.e. the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Further Processing of such introduced Personal Data by the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party for own purposes or for purposes of Third Parties is not permitted, unless permitted under the Data Protection Legislation (including as expressly permitted in the informed consent, if any).
 - (2) The Personal Data being introduced to the Action or Processed shall be adequate in relation to the purpose of the transfer and the Processing. No Personal Data shall be transferred and Processed if it is not necessary for the stated purpose. Further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purpose subject to the conditions set out in the Data Protection Legislation.
 - (3) Personal Data shall be retained in a form which permits identification of Data Subjects no longer than necessary for the purposes of the Project, (unless longer storage is permitted under and subject to the conditions set out in the applicable Data Protection Legislation), within the limitations of applicable laws.
 - (4) The introducing Beneficiary shall inform the Data Subjects about the transfer of their Personal Data to and the Processing by the accessing Beneficiary and if applicable Third Parties if and to the extent required under Data Protection Legislation. The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party shall provide the introducing Beneficiary with all information about the accessing and Processing of the

Personal Data which the introducing Beneficiary requests in order to inform the Data Subjects according to applicable law.

- (5) The introducing and accessing Beneficiary/Third Party, respectively are the responsible contact for any requests by the Data Subjects, e.g. for information, correction or deletion of the Personal Data or Human Samples or for an objection to the Processing, the case being.
- (6) The introducing and accessing Beneficiary/Third Party shall take all reasonable technical and organizational measures necessary to protect the introduced Personal Data against unauthorized or unlawful Processing and against accidental loss, destruction of or damage to such Personal Data, in accordance with article 3.3.
- (7) The introducing Beneficiary is entitled to perform an audit of the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party Processes Personal Data both during the term of the Action and for seven (7) years after the completion of the Action in accordance with the provisions of this Consortium Agreement. For this purpose, the accessing Beneficiary will inform the introducing Beneficiary/Third Party upon request and provide necessary documents and information to the introducing Beneficiary/Third Party. The accessing Beneficiary is obliged to perform internal audits to ensure compliance with its obligations.

3.8 The transfer of Personal Data on a Controller-to-Controller basis does not modify the acknowledgment and/or allocation of intellectual property rights of Clauses 6, 7 and 8 of this Consortium Agreement. This transfer shall only be the consequence of honoring the rights (e.g., ownership, licenses or Access Rights) that both the introducing Beneficiary and the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party shall have on the relevant Background and Results according to Clauses 6, 7 and 8 of this Consortium Agreement.

3.9 **Controller to Processor Actions.** To the extent the Beneficiary introduces to the Action Personal Data that are accessed and Processed by other Beneficiaries or Third Parties only on behalf and instructions of the introducing Beneficiary ("**Controller to Processor**"), the introducing Beneficiary (Controller) and the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party (Processor) are additionally obliged as follows:²

- (1) The introducing Beneficiary shall only use those Beneficiaries or Third Parties as Processors that provide sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures in such a manner that Processing will meet the requirements of the Data Protection Legislation and ensure the protection of the rights of the Data Subject.
- (2) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor shall not engage another Processor without prior specific or general written authorisation of the Controller. In the case of general written authorisation, the Processor shall inform the Controller of any intended changes concerning the addition or replacement of other Processors, thereby giving the Controller the opportunity to object to such changes. Where the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor does engages another Processor for carrying out specific processing activities on behalf of the

² Clause 3.6 may also become relevant in case that the consortium establishes databases and/or human sample repositories. In this case the Beneficiary responsible for database/repository may be considered a Processor so that Clause 3.6 would apply. Please also note that the prerequisites established in this Clause 3.6 may have to be supplemented with additional wording according to the national legal requirements for commissioned data processing.

Controller, the same data protection obligations as set out in the contract or other legal act between the Controller and the Processor as referred to in article 3.8 (3) shall be imposed on that other processor by way of a contract or other legal act, in particular providing sufficient guarantees to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures in such a manner that the processing will meet the requirements of the Data Protection Legislation. Where that other Processor fails to fulfil its data protection obligations, the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as initial Processor shall remain fully liable to the Controller for the performance of that other Processor's obligations

- (3) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party shall Process Personal Data exclusively in the name of and in accordance with the documented instructions of the introducing Beneficiary, including with regard to the transfer of Personal Data to a Third Country unless required to do so by Union or Member State law to which the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor is subject; in such a case, the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor shall inform the Controller of that legal requirement before processing, unless that law prohibits such information on important grounds of public interest (Commissioned Data processing). The introducing Beneficiary remains the Controller and responsible for the legality of Processing Personal Data. Processing by the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party shall be governed by a contract or other legal act, that is binding on the accessing Beneficiary/Third Party with regard to the Controller and that sets out the subject-matter and duration of the Processing, the nature and purpose of the Processing, the type of Personal Data and categories of Data Subjects and the obligations and rights of the Controller.
- (4) The Processing of the Personal Data by the accessing Beneficiary shall exclusively and entirely occur in the type and extent and for the purposes (or further processing if and to the extent allowed under Data Protection Legislation).
- (5) The accessing Beneficiary /Third Party as Processor shall be regarded as Processor and shall not acquire any rights with respect to the Personal Data.
- (6) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor will ensure that persons it authorises to Process the Personal Data comply with the duties set forth in Section 3.4.
- (7) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor will implement appropriate, technical and organizational measures to ensure a level of security appropriate to protect the Personal Data against unauthorized or unlawful Processing and against accidental loss, destruction of or damage to such Personal Data in accordance with Section 3.3.
- (8) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor will, by appropriate technical and organisational measures, assist the Controller insofar as this is possible, for the fulfilment of the Controller's obligation to respond to requests for exercising the Data Subject's rights, taking into account the nature of the processing.
- (9) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor will assist the Controller, upon its request, in ensuring compliance with the obligations relating to the security of processing, data breach notifications, data protection impact assessment and prior consultation to the Data Protection Authority, taking into account the nature of the Processing and the information available to the

Processor. In any case, the Processor will report to the Controller any data breach without undue delay and at the latest within 24 hours after having become aware of it and provide the Controller with all relevant information in that regard.

(10) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor shall return all the Personal Data to the Controller after the end of the provision of services relating to processing, and delete existing copies (unless applicable law requires storage of the Personal Data).

(11) The accessing Beneficiary/Third Party as Processor shall make available to the Controller all information necessary to demonstrate compliance with the obligations laid down in this section 3.8, and allow for and contribute to audits, including inspections, conducted by the controller or another auditor mandated by the Controller.

3.10 **Joint Controller Actions.** To the extent joint controllership is established with regard to determining the purposes and the means of the Processing, the Joint Controllers shall in a transparent manner determine their respective responsibilities for compliance with the obligations under the Data Protection Legislation, in particular as regards the exercising of the rights of the Data Subject and their respective duties to provide the information to the Data Subjects as required under Data Protection Legislation by means of an arrangement between them unless, and in so far as, the respective responsibilities of the Joint Controllers are determined by applicable law to which the Joint Controllers are subject. The arrangement referred shall duly reflect the respective roles and relationships of the Joint Controllers vis-à-vis the Data Subjects.

3.11 In general, cells lines (e.g. HeLa), derivatives (e.g. isolated proteins) and preparations of human biological materials (e.g. sub-cellular fractions) that are well established and made available for research use, do not require re-consent and/or ethics committee/IRB approval for the intended research use. Beneficiaries will need to make a case-by-case analysis, in order to determine whether consent is required or not.

4. FURTHER PROVISIONS ON THE USE OF PERSONAL DATA IN THE ACTION

4.1 Beneficiaries are responsible for their Processing, storing, using and transferring of Personal Data in compliance with the applicable Data Protection Legislation.

4.2 The Beneficiary introducing the Personal Data to the Action shall immediately inform the other Beneficiaries in writing in case that the Data Subjects have withdrawn their consent (taking into account that the consequences of such withdrawal may be restricted under the Data Protection Legislation).

4.3 If and to the extent required under the Data Protection Legislation, additional individual Data Subject consent and ethics committee/IRB approval must be obtained when the research use intended is inconsistent with or beyond the scope of the original consent.

4.4 If and to the extent required under the Data Protection Legislation, additional consent should also be obtained if the original consent (where needed under Data Protection Legislation) did not include analysis of DNA and other genetic tests (if relevant to the research proposal) or use of any associated medical information (if relevant to the research proposal).

- 4.5 If and to the extent required under the Data Protection Legislation, in circumstances where individual re-consent (were initial informed consent was needed) cannot practicably be obtained, approval of an ethics committee or IRB (if permissible under applicable Data Protection Legislation) must be sought to determine whether the research can proceed in the absence of individual consent, as permissible under the applicable laws and regulations.
- 4.6 If the Processing or intended Processing of Personal Data by a Beneficiary or Third Party, as data Controller or data Processor, takes place in a third country (i.e. a country outside the European Economic Area) which do not offer an adequate level of protection, this processing shall be carried out in accordance with the requirements and appropriate safeguards under the Data Protection Legislation, such as, entering into EU standard contractual clauses.